

The Implementation of Oplan Tokhang in Iriga City

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Abstract:- This Anti-Drug Campaign is a current domestic government propaganda campaign in the world with the goal of influencing the attitude of the public toward drug abuse and of preventing drug abuse among people all over the world. It is part of a global effort to prevent drug abuse among people all over the world. A person's safety and healthy living must be prioritized above the use of illicit substances, so that in the near future, the likelihood of committing suicide or other crimes would be reduced to a minuscule percentage. Illegal narcotics may also cause a significant devastation of the mind, as well as despair and tension, if used excessively. This study assessed the adherence of the Iriga City Police Station Personnel on the implementation of Philippine National Police Memorandum Circular number 16 series of 2016 or "OplanTokhang" towards a drug-cleared community. Specifically, it aims to attain the following objectives: Identify the level of implementation of OplanTokhang in Iriga City. The researcher utilized the Quantitative method of research in the conduct of the study. The respondents were identified in theselected Barangays of Iriga City and member in charge in the Philippine National Police . The instrument used in this study was a set of constructed questionnaires. Findings revealedbased on the result of the study the clearing of all barangays on the said city was moderately attained and the same on the implementation of the second phase of the said memorandum circular. This would imply that without the proper assistance of each agency that is supposed to be religious in its role, the whole approach or process will be affected. Frontline of the government that has a direct link to the community . It serves as the eye and ears of the interagency and whole of nation approach and without seriousness on the implementation of the guidelines set by the reference mentioned above it will create a domino effect on the system.

Keywords:- Anti-Drug Campaign, War on Drugs, Oplantokhang, Iriga City.

I. INTRODUCTION

OplanTokhang which aimed to personally talk to those involved in illegal drugs convincing them to stop and surrender to authorities for investigation, verification and rehabilitation, has been seen effective for more and more suspected drug users and pushers are turning themselves to the police. Since the said program gives chance to suspected individuals involved in illegal drugs to change themselves and become one of the good citizens, arrests and killings can be avoided in case they put up a fight with the authorities in the future. And according to Regional Prosecutor Jaime Umpa, the said campaign may greatly reduce the number of

drug-related cases that reach Office of Regional Prosecutor in Northern Mindanao (Badal, 2016)

International papers report on the trade of illegal drugs particularly its production, distribution and increasing rates of consumption in all parts of the world. Heroin seizures in 2008, reached a record high of 73.7 metric tons mostly in Middle East and South-West Asia, South-East Europe, and Western and Central Europe.

In the North American market, cocaine is usually transported which would originate by in Colombia to Mexico or to Central America by sea and then to the United States and Canada by land. This drug called Cocaine is transferred by sea in vessel/s. It is in this country, Colombia which produces the main source of the cocaine found in Europe. Trading also common in Peru and the State of Bolivia as compared in the United States market.

Almost all humanities are affected by the illegal drug trade and consumption is a continuing threat to the lives of the people.

In the West and Central Asia, Afghanistan still dominates the cultivation of opium in 2015 and accounts for its two thirds space in the drug market. Europe is trading supplies with Afghan providers through the "Balkan route", through Turkey, South-Eastern Europe, and the Islamic Republic of Iran, which is investigated to be the main channel for heroin marketing.

The transnational view describes that interventions of international leaders in the continuing proliferation of illegal drugs particularly the consequences to the younger generation.

If left unmonitored, Asia will become a vulnerable target of drug syndicates that would destroy the physical, intellectual, psychological and emotional well-being of the people mostly the youth and young adults.

In fact, the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) who is the lead anti-drug law enforcement agency, responsible for preventing, investigating and combating any dangerous drugs, controlled precursors and essential chemicals within the Philippines reported the status of the country's campaign and reports linking to the OplanTokhang.

The war on Drugs of President Rodrigo RoaDuterte still face similar challenge in as far as hitting the core group of this drug syndicate. Since 2016, the government relaunched the controversial anti-drug campaign, known locally as OplanTokhang, despite people known as vigilantes

questioning the legality of the operation which are seen as massive human rights violations.

In Region V, the relaunching took place in Legazpi City through a fun walk dubbed as “L.A.K.A.D. Tokhang 2” which stands for Lipulin at Kalampaginang Droga. Its main objective was to increase public awareness on the ill-effects of hard drugs and encouraged participants to actively get involved in the national campaign against illegal substances.

The City of Iriga, known for its peaceful abode supported PNP ANTI-ILLEGAL DRUGS CAMPAIGN PLAN - PROJECT: “DOUBLE BARREL” commonly called “OplanTokhang” (Toktok-Hangyo), aimed to personally talk to those involved in illegal drugs convincing them to stop and surrender to authorities for investigation, verification and rehabilitation, has been seen effective for more and more suspected drug users and pushers are turning themselves to the police. Since the said program gives chance to suspected individuals involved in illegal drugs to change 2 themselves and become one of the good citizens, arrests and killings can be avoided in case they put up a fight with the authorities in the future. And according to Regional Prosecutor Jaime Umpa, the said campaign may greatly reduce the number of drug-related cases that reach Office of Regional Prosecutor in Northern Mindanao (Badal, 2016)

The Philippine National Police in this city is under mission order to clear all drug affected barangays across the country, conduct no let up operations against illegal drugs personalities and dismantle drug syndicates. (COMMAND MEMORANDUM CIRCULAR NO. 16 – (2016), Estacio, (2018) describes the type of surrenderers in the OplanTokhang. It was found out that most of them were users rather than pushers or involved in drug trafficking. The productive years of individuals who are either in school and no employment were using shabu and marijuana. The age bracket of the users was in their mid-adolescent years. Some who uses these drugs for 1 to 2 years, were considered mild users. Peer influence, family problems, personal problems, unresolved relationships, unemployment, and associations with friends or relatives taking drugs are one of the factors related to drug use. The Barangay Anti-Drug Abuse Council in the City of Iriga is continuously rendering a twenty-four-seven monitoring or “ronda” activity in the five communities to assist the PNP-Iriga implement the goal of the project double barrel. It is observed that people who are into drugs are usually selling household items, or committing crimes such as theft, robbery or drug pushing just to sustain their adverse addiction. Individuals who are afraid to be killed by the police submits themselves voluntarily to the headquarters for rehabilitation. Others who have recovered would likely participate in “No to Drugs” campaign in the city of Iriga.

EUSEBIO, (2018), analyzed the level of effectiveness of OplanTokhang in relation to drug reported incidents in the Municipality of Piat. Respondents of the study were the PNP Personnel of Piat Police Station and selected residents of the identified community of the Municipality of Piat. It was found out that the Philippine National Police in this municipality is very effective in

enforcing OplanTokhang. The following manifestations showed absence of crime related to drugs in the locality. The PNP are motivated to do their job to maintain peace and order in the community. The study is similar to the present research as it also focused on the initiatives of the police force in safeguarding the constituents of the city. The different activities conducted by the BADAC in collaboration with the PNP is an effective means to provide awareness on the menace of drug abuse and drug trade.

Hunt, (2020) found out that the reporting of government and non-government newspapers placed dissimilar focus on Project Tokhang. The accountability of the victims of drug related killings reached to an estimated toll of 7,000 increasing to 14,000 persons including innocent bystanders, and law enforcers. The print media suggested measures in improving the approaches of law enforcers and device to monitor the process of engagement. Interventions were not of priority in the initial implementation of OplanTokhang, rather, executing an iron hand in the process. The significance of the findings is different from the present study in terms of strengthening the proactive approach of the PNP Iriga and the barangay councils of the five barangays.

On July 1, 2016 President Duterte announced in a press release that he would eliminate the use of illicit drugs. The best way to achieve the plan is to authorize the PNP to implement Project Tokhang in all parts of the country. was implemented by the Philippine National Police (PNP). This implementation “involves the conduct of house visitations to persuade suspected illegal drug personalities to stop their illegal drug activities” (Dela Rosa, 2016). The national drug policy consisted of a simultaneous approach of targeting both drug supply and demand under a divided policy named “Double Barrel” (Dela Rosa, 2016). The Project “High Value Target” aims to eradicate the chain of illegal drug supply in the regions, provinces, and cities and even reaching to remote areas frequently distributed by the international syndicates. Another policy of Project Tokhang aimed to clear the local communities or barangay/s from holding illegal activities of using and selling drugs. (Gonzales, Cabigao, &Cellona, 2016) is the focus of this content analysis.

Mirasol(2017)the Philippines is considered a major transshipment point and destination country for methamphetamine (shabu) . President Rodrigo Duterte initiated the *war on drugs* at the beginning of his term, through a campaign against illicit drug trade that serves as the basis of domestic policy. The Philippines seeks to eradicate drug dealing and addiction, which are seen by the present administration as main challenge to the country’s economic and social development. The Philippine National Police released new guidelines for OplanTokhang. Under the new rules are the Creation, updating of the drug watchlist. The is the bible of OplanTokhang for this serves as the basis for their profiling, monitoring and operation for high value targets, users most commonly, or pushers. Only validated names by the PNP Directorate for Intelligence (DI) are queued. Not just anyone from the PNP can become a member of the tokhang teams. Through selection is required, numerous training is participated. The team must have at least 4 cop members, led

by those ranked police inspector and up. There should be one representative, a member of the Anti-Drug Abuse Council (ADAC) from the barangay, PNP Human Rights Affairs Office (HRAO) representative or a civilian human rights advocate. The guidelines on pre-deployment preparations, “Knock then Plead”, documentations and referrals, after activity report and evaluation and accountability.

Martinez, et.al (2019) argued that the ‘war on drugs’ has caused thousands of children and youth in poor communities in Metro Manila into a defenseless, confused and troubled condition, their state of mind, psychological well-being fell into deep insecurity, depression and feeling of injustice. Children who became orphaned, alone due to the loss of loved ones, parents or guardians had but only painful and traumatic memories of tokhang. The OplanTokhang is not a humane way of bringing peace and justice to the poor. It only gave them fear in the absence of due process that rich and influential people, those who are connected with the powerful and people in authority, enjoys. To address this dilemma, there should be a human security for orphaned children and their families

Based on the record of the Iriga City Police Station that out of thirty-six (36) barangays there were still seventeen (17) uncleared barangays of the said city. The Department of Interior and Local Government’s Barangay Anti-Drug Abuse Council (BADAC) functionality self-assessment and audit of the said barangays shows that majority of the Barangay officials were rated as “Moderate level of Functionality” meaning majority of the functions of the BADAC were not adhered by its members. This reflects the big picture of the level of implementation of the said target locale about the OplanTokhang.

This covers the thirty-six barangays and of which five barangay are within the vicinity of the Central Business District namely Barangays San Miguel, San Roque, San Juan, San Francisco, and San Nicolas.

This study will determine the success of the Philippine National Police’s operation in delivering its mission and goal according to PNP anti-illegal drugs campaign plan - project: double barrel.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

II. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, population and locale of the study, data gathering tools, gathering procedures, and the treatment data.

The researcher will make use of the descriptive quantitative research approach specifically utilizing survey questionnaire as primary research instrument to assess the implementation of OplanTokhang in the City of Iriga specifically in the five barangays: San Miguel, San Francisco, San Juan, San Roque and San Nicolas,

According to Subong and Beldia (2005), a descriptive research involves collection of data to answer questions about current status of the study. To Kumar, (2011), “a study in which the main focus is on description, rather than examining relationships or associations, is classified as descriptive study.

➤ *Population and Locale of the Study*

The researcher will engage a minimum of ten (10) regular members of the Philippine National Police of Iriga City, five members of the Barangay council including the representative of BADAC. Purposive sampling technique will be used in this study. According to Palinkas (2016), purposeful sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources. This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest.

➤ *Data Gathering Tools*

In line with the research design, several data gathering methods will be employed to include the following: questionnaires, document analysis, audio recorder, informed

consent form and archival/document analysis will also be prepared.

➤ *Data Gathering Procedures*

Upon endorsement by the Professor and the Dean of UC-CCJE and the coordinator of the Graduate School (UC-CCJE), the researcher will secure permission to conduct the study to the Head of the Philippine National Police in Iriga City, Camarines Sur, Barangay Chairman of Barangay San Miguel, San Francisco, San Roque, San Juan and San Nicolas. Following the approval, the researcher will start the collection of qualitative data. The researcher will plan the schedule for the conduct of interview. Participants will be given orientation as to the purpose of the study before the initial conduct and proceedings of the interview.

➤ *Ethical Protocol and Principles*

In the collection of data, ethical issues are inevitable, thus, several ethical principles will be emphasized in order to guarantee the utmost integrity, confidentiality in protecting the rights of the respondents as well as in preserving reliability, validity and the credibility and anonymity of the information gathered. For this study, the researcher will consider the following ethical protocols throughout the research process:

Consent. Prior to the collection of data, endorsement from the Professor and Dean of College of Criminal Justice Education will be secured. Then individual informed consent shall be obtained from the research participants before engaging them into in-depth interviews. It will be made clear to them that their participation is voluntary and discrimination will not take place against those who would not want to participate.

Confidentiality and Anonymity. All data observed and information taken from the research participants will be coded to ensure confidentiality. Recordings (video or audio) shall be properly secured and will be fully destroyed as soon as the research report is finalized and submitted. Code names will be assigned to the respondents particularly in the qualitative portion so as not to reveal their real names and profile.

➤ *Treatment of the Data*

Descriptive statistics was used in the course of the investigation to examine the variable under consideration specifically on the level of attainment of the Iriga City PNP on the objectives of the OplanTokhang. It was utilized for the researcher's final assessment of the data acquired from the information provided by the respondents was carried out. This will be critical in the identification of difficulties that are encountered, as well as the discovery of potential improvements or innovations for the aforementioned Anti-Drug abuse program.

The result of the survey in studies objectives was treated and discussed quantitatively. Likert scale was used to describe the items in the questionnaire, with a descriptive value of 4, highly attained; 3, attained; 2, moderately attained; and 1, Not attained for problem number 1 and 4, highly effective 3, effective 2, moderately effective and 1 not effective to the problem number 2. Result of which, was analyzed using frequency distribution and weighted mean.

The following formula was used:

$$WM = \frac{f(W)}{N}$$

Where:

- WM = Weighted Mean
- F = frequency
- W = weight
- N = Number of Respondents

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents a detailed discussion of the result of the study after the data gathering and analysis of all available data and the data provided to the researcher by the respondents.

➤ *The Extent of Attainment of The Objectives of Oplan Tokhang*

First part presents the level of attainment of the Iriga City PNP on MC 16 series of 2016 or OplanTokhang objectives. Specifically on clearing all drug-affected barangays in the entire city of Iriga, Camarines Sur, the conduct of not let up operations against illegal drug personalities, dismantle drug syndicate. Equally, address the illegal drug problem in the barangay, Pursue neutralization of illegal drug personalities as well as the backbone of illegal drugs network operation in the City.

Table 1:- The Extent of Attainment of The Objectives of Oplan Tokhang

INDICATORS	PNP WM	DR	BADAC WM	DR
Clear all drug-affected barangays in the entire city of Iriga, Camarines Sur.	1.65	MA	2.06	MA
Conduct not let up operations against illegal drug personalities.	3.78	HA	3.89	HA
Dismantle drug syndicate.	3.95	HA	3.62	HA
Equally, address the illegal drug problem in the barangay.	3.89	HA	3.45	HA
Pursue neutralization of illegal drug personalities as well as the backbone of illegal drugs network operation in the City.	3.66	HA	3.54	HA

Table 1 shows the extent of attainment of the objectives of oplantokhang by the Iriga City PNP as assessed by the personnel themselves and the members of the BADAC. The result were: Clear all drug-affected barangays in the entire city of Iriga, Camarines Sur got 1.65 or **Moderately Attained** according to the PNP while 2.06 from the members of the BADAC or also **Moderately Attained**. Meanwhile, the second indicator is Conduct not let up operations against illegal drug personalities got 3.78 or **Highly Attained** according to the PNP while, 3.62 from the members of the BADAC or also **Highly Attained**. On the other hand, dismantle drug syndicate Equally, addressing the illegal drug problem in the barangay and Pursue neutralization of illegal drug personalities as well as the backbone of illegal drugs network operation in the City all got **Highly Attained** mean rating both from the PNP and the BADAC members.

The significant variable that was presented on the table refers to the first indicator that to “Clear all drug-affected barangays in the entire city of Iriga, Camarines Sur” it was obvious that there were still barangays on the said city that up until now not recognized as drug cleared barangays. This would imply that without the proper assistance of each agency that is supposed to be religious in its role, the whole approach or process will be affected. Frontline of the government that has a direct link to the community and the

PWUDs. It serves as the eye and ears of the interagency and whole of nation approach and without seriousness on the implementation of the guidelines set by the reference mentioned above it will create a domino effect on the system. According to Johnson & Fernquest (2018) with the support of the barangay is a cohesive group of inhabitants possessing commitment and performing a well-defined and significant role that can be transformed into effective and harmonious action for the prevention and control of crime and delinquency. Moreover, in her findings as cited in the study drug Prevention Campaign in the Philippines was designed to contribute to the reduction in intake of illicit drugs among all sectors of society by raising the public’s awareness and participation. The program is designed to educate the public of the different kinds of illegal drugs and issues associated with them.

➤ *The Level of Implementation of Oplan Tokhang In Iriga City*

This second part presents the level of implementation of oplantokhang in iriga city. Specifically, collection and validation if Information, coordination, house to house visitation, processing and Documentation and, monitoring and evaluation.

Table 2:- The Level of Implementation of Oplan Tokhang In Iriga City

INDICATORS	PNP WM	DR	BADAC WM	DR
1. Collection and Validation of Information	3.78	HE	3.90	HE
2. Coordination	1.70	ME	1.35	ME
3. House to house visitation	3.13	HE	3.62	HE
4. Processing and Documentation	3.01	HE	3.14	HE
5. Monitoring and Evaluation	3.26	HE	3.38	HE

Table 2 presents the assessment of the implementation of the OplanTokhang in Iriga City as assessed by the personnel themselves and the members of the BADAC. Implementation here refers to the level of adherence of the PNP Iriga on the Philippine National Police Memorandum Circular no.16 series of 2016 or PNP Anti-illegal drug campaign plan – project “double barrel” mode of execution. Generally, the findings show that collection and validation of Information rated by PNP with weighted mean of 3.78 or “Highly Effective” while the BADAC with weighted mean 3.90 or “Highly Effective”; House to house visitation rated by PNP with weighted mean of 3.13 or “Highly Effective” while the BADAC with weighted mean 3.62 or “Highly Effective”; Processing and Documentation rated by PNP with weighted mean of 3.01 or “Highly Effective” while the BADAC with weighted mean 3.14 or “Highly Effective”; and Monitoring and Evaluation rated by PNP with weighted mean of 3.26 or “Highly Effective” while the BADAC with weighted mean 3.38 or “Highly Effective”. on the other hand, only Coordination was rated “Moderately Effective” by PNP with weighted mean of 1.70 while the BADAC with weighted mean 1.35.

Understanding coordination work in policing is important for a number of reasons—probably most obviously,

when law enforcement fail to coordinate their activities adequately, crimes and their detection and prosecution can slip through organizational cracks. Supported by the study conducted by Priyosantoso et al. (2022) that these issues of coordination are not limited to interactions between organizations. Indeed, sociological studies of all kinds of organizations show that the ways in which actors coordinate within an organization are also rarely straightforward and often marked by internal competition or schism. In public organizations particularly, different sections of the organization may quite coherently be oriented at cross-purposes from one another.

IV. CONCLUSION

1. The first objective Clear all drug-affected barangays in the entire city of Iriga, Camarines Sur. It was discovered that it was rated as moderately attained. The result reflects the actual status of the anti-drug campaign productivity of the Iriga Police Station. It was noted during the preliminary inquiry by the researcher presented on the initial part of this paper the actual number of the barangay on the said City that was categorized as uncleared.

2. One of the common reasons that was presented to the researcher was the lack of cooperation and coordination as to

the reporting of drug related incidents on the barangay. There were also instances according to the accounts of the PNP that some of the drug personalities in the Barangays were advised by the purok leaders and barangay officials to just leave the locality to avoid detection that may result to illegitimate course of action. This paper had achieved its purpose of determining the level attainment of the objectives and effectiveness of the OplanTokhang in the City of Iriga.

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